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BREAST CANCER MORTALITY IN ELDERLY WOMEN IN NORTHEAST BRAZIL: FROM 1996 TO 2020

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this article is to present breast cancer mortality in the Northeast region of Brazil, among elderly women aged 60 to 80 years or older, from 1996 to 2020. Data from the Mortality Information System (SIM) of the Department of Information Technology of the Unified Health System (DATASUS) and the International Classification of Diseases (ICD) were used, as well as data from the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE). Breast cancer is considered the most common type of cancer among women in all Brazilian regions. By 2030, the Northeast region of Brazil will have the highest cancer mortality rate, according to a study by Barbosa et al (2015).

Keywords: Mortality. Breast Cancer. Elderly Women.

INTRODUCTION

Breast cancer is the most common type of cancer among women and the leading cause of cancer death worldwide.

Breast cancer occurs when there is excessive and disordered cell proliferation, resulting from genetic modifications that stimulate increased estrogen levels. Thus, women are more predisposed than men due to their greater breast tissue. Because it is a pathology associated with high mortality rates, it is important to adopt measures for prevention and early detection.

Without considering non-melanoma skin tumors, female breast cancer occupies the first most frequent position in all Brazilian regions, with an estimated risk of 81.06 per 100,000 in the Southeast Region; 71.16 per 100,000 in the South Region; 45.24 per 100,000 in the Central-West Region; 44.29 per 100,000 in the Northeast Region; and 21.34 per 100,000 in the North Region.

Access to health services differs across several Brazilian states, and consequently, there is a wide variation in mortality rates due to disparities in the initial diagnosis, treatment, and follow-up.

From the 1990s onwards, changes began in the clinical presentation and management of breast cancer cases, with the implementation of mammography screening, the implementation of effective hormonal treatments, chemotherapy, and progress in surgery and radiotherapy.

In many countries, these innovations have contributed to reduced mortality and increased survival from breast cancer.

However, in developing countries like Brazil, where mammography screening is performed opportunistically, resulting in loss of patient history information, it is difficult to assess the quality of screening programs. Furthermore, factors such as the disorganization of the patient care network are also contributing to this. With cancer, triggering problems that determine the levels mortality for this cancer, because the fatal cases are influenced by early

diagnosis and the availability of treatments and patient care.

Beginning in 2000, discussions began on actions that could integrate breast cancer control into the existing Viva Mulher Program, which focused on cervical cancer prevention. Then, in 2002, INCA and the Ministry of Health intensified the Viva Mulher Program's efforts, expanding cervical cancer screening coverage nationwide and including breast cancer-related initiatives. Gradually, the Program became known as the National Cervical and Breast Cancer Control Program.

Population aging is occurring rapidly in developing countries, especially in Brazil. Thus, this process of demographic change represents a major challenge for these countries, which urgently need to incorporate the issue of population aging into public policy formulation and devise solutions for social and health reorganization sufficient to meet the needs of this new population reality. (MIRANDA, GMD, 2016; VERAS, R. 2009)

Thus, studies on this pathology gain even more prominence in the national context, as Brazil is undergoing a rapid process of population aging, which has directly increased the incidence and mortality of chronic non-communicable diseases (PEREA et al., 2018), (CARVALHO; PAES, 2019).

It is estimated that by 2025, there will be approximately 1.2 billion people over the age of 60 worldwide. Alongside the demographic transition, the population's pattern of illness and death is also undergoing transformations. The epidemiological profile, which is the result of a complex series of interrelated changes in health and disease behavior that occur in populations over time, is a consequence of a set of social, economic, and, primarily, demographic transformations.

Information on breast cancer incidence and mortality can be useful for planning public policies and implementing evidence-based cancer control programs, but it is not available in most low- and middle-income countries. Therefore, it is necessary to analyze information

on the epidemiological behavior of deaths from this disease, enabling the establishment of prevention and health promotion strategies, with a reduction in public spending on treatment.

Conceptualization and Risk Factors

Breast cancer is a multifactorial disease, with age being the most important risk factor. However, other environmental and behavioral factors increase the risk of developing cancer, such as obesity, a sedentary lifestyle, alcohol consumption, and frequent exposure to ionizing radiation; reproductive and hormonal history (early menarche, nulliparity, first pregnancy after age 30, late menopause, use of hormonal contraceptives); and finally, genetic and hereditary factors (family history of ovarian and breast cancer, genetic alterations, especially in the BRCA1 and BRCA2 genes) (INCA, 2019).

Cancer is already a serious public health problem throughout Brazil. The widespread knowledge that advanced age is one of the main risk factors associated with this disease is relevant. Therefore, we must encourage and motivate women to prevent breast cancer through good nutrition, physical activity, judicious medication use, and adherence to screening.

Diagnosis

The main signs and symptoms of breast cancer are a lump in the breast and/or armpit, which may be painless or cause breast pain, and changes in the skin covering the breast, such as retractions with an appearance similar to orange peel, discharge of clear or bloody secretion, unilateral or bilateral.

For early detection of breast cancer, it is recommended:

- Annual screening, through clinical breast examination, for all women aged 40 and older. This procedure is still considered part of comprehensive women's health care and should be performed at all clinical appointments, regardless of age group;

- Mammography screening in women aged between 50 and 69 years, with a maximum interval of two years between exams;
- Clinical breast examination and annual mammography, from the age of 35, for women belonging to population groups with a high risk of developing breast cancer;
- Guaranteed access to diagnosis, treatment and follow-up for all women with changes in the tests performed.

The following population groups are defined as having a high risk of developing breast cancer: 1) Women with a family history of at least one first-degree relative (mother, sister or daughter) diagnosed with breast cancer, under 50 years of age; 2) Women with a family history of at least one first-degree relative (mother, sister or daughter) diagnosed with bilateral breast cancer or ovarian cancer, in any age group; 3) Women with a family history of male breast cancer; 4) Women with a histopathological diagnosis of proliferative breast lesion with atypia or lobular neoplasia in situ.

According to the Ministry of Health, the most effective forms of early detection are clinical breast examination (CBE) and mammography (MMG). Ultrasound can be performed as diagnostic support, and FNA and core biopsy can provide sufficient data for clinical staging of the tumor and treatment planning. However, many women at risk do not have access to these exams because the healthcare system in some parts of Brazil is slow and extremely bureaucratic.

When breast cancer is diagnosed early, characterized as "in situ," it has a high cure rate, resulting in a 97% five-year survival rate. The most widely used method for evaluating outcomes in oncology, and even epidemiology, is patient survival, in which mortality rates in historical series have high analytical significance, making it possible to discuss statistical techniques for survival analysis with observations obtained from health service records.

METHODOLOGY

An ecological, retrospective time-series study was carried out, based on secondary data collected from the Mortality Information System (SIM) of the Department of Information Technology of the Unified Health System (Datusus), with analysis of deaths resulting from malignant breast neoplasm that occurred in the northeastern region of Brazil in the period from 1996 to 2020. In addition to demographic data from the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE), based on information from the census (2000 and 2010), count (1996); and population estimates for the other years.

To analyze temporal mortality trends, the Joinpoint Regression Analysis program was used. It allows computing and analyzing rate trends in segments, providing models that summarize behavior over the period. The specifications used in the program were the model: $\log(y) = bx$, where Y is the mortality rate and X is the year of death. Constant variance was assumed, using a maximum of four joinpoints. The joinpoint determination method used was Grid Search (LGS), and the model selection method used was the permutation test.

Two-tailed tests with a 5% significance level were used for all calculations. Epidat software version 3.1 was used to calculate confidence intervals and adjust rates.

Knowledge about the incidence and mortality of neoplasms aims to support public policy structures that aim at early diagnosis and adequate treatment of these diseases, as well as their associated comorbidities. (DUTRA; PARREIRA; GUIMARÃES, 2018).

Changes in society's lifestyle over the years have accompanied an increase in cancer incidence and mortality. However, disparities between nations related to socioeconomic and cultural characteristics influence prevention, control, and quality of life policies for patients after diagnosis. While developed countries have reduced cancer incidence and mortality rates, poor and developing countries like Brazil account for 80% of the world's

noncommunicable diseases, and cancer will be the leading cause of morbidity and mortality in these regions in the coming decades. (BRAY et al, 2012).

In 2030, the northeastern region of Brazil will have the highest cancer mortality rate, according to a study by Barbosa et al (2015).

The Mortality Information System (SIM) was essential for this study, as it provides important information for describing the national mortality profile. The various variables that feed this system are collected from death certificates, including: year of death, place of residence of the deceased, sex, age group, race/ethnicity, education level, and cause of death. One of the most important pieces of information is the underlying cause of death, which is coded based on the International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems, or simply the International Classification of Diseases (ICD-10). The purpose of this system is to standardize and catalog diseases and health problems according to the International Nomenclature of Diseases established by the WHO (World Health Organization). Beginning in 1996, death certificates in Brazil began to be coded using the 10th Revision of the International Classification of Diseases (ICD-10). The SIM (Mortality Information System) gathers death records from municipal and state health departments and disseminates information to the community on general aspects or disaggregated by specific variables (DUARTE; BARRETO, 2015)

PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

Table 1 shows the information quality indicators by age group (60-80 years or older) for the population of northeastern Brazil, analyzing deaths from ill-defined causes and malignant neoplasms without location specification (ICD C80). A significant reduction can be observed over the years, starting in 2003, across all age groups. However, from 1997 to 2003, the number of women over 80 years of age more than doubled that of women aged 60

years old regarding ill-defined causes. Deaths from ill-defined causes have also decreased in recent decades in all Brazilian regions, particularly in municipalities outside the capitals. This indicates an improvement in the quality of information recorded in the Mortality Information System (SIM). However, significant numbers of deaths from ill-defined causes remain in the North and Northeast regions.

The World Health Organization (WHO), which compiles the latest available data for each country on deaths from ill-defined causes (IDCs), reported a 10.14% rate for Brazil in 2015. Other South American countries, such as Argentina (16.66%), Ecuador (11.81%), Paraguay (14.41%), and Uruguay (15.96%), have higher rates than Brazil, while Peru (6%), Guyana (8.72%), Colombia (4.69%), and Chile (4.6%) have rates of less than 10% of deaths from ill-defined causes. In comparison, in 2003, European countries had death coverage close to 100%, while African countries had coverage of less than 10%. Africa had the highest number of countries with no or low-quality mortality data. In South America, data quality ranged from low to medium.

Regarding malignant neoplasms without specification of location, all women in the age groups studied (60 years; 60-69 years; 70-79 years; 80 years) presented similar percentages to each other and comparatively all results decreased between 1997 and 2003.

Table 2 shows the crude rate and mortality rate ratio for breast cancer in the Northeast region, according to age group in the periods 1997-2008 and 2009-2020. Mortality rates were calculated per 100,000 inhabitants/year.

The findings of the present study showed an increase in the mortality rate from breast cancer in elderly women, in all age groups (60-69 years; 70-79 years; 80 years or older). In 1997, women in the age group between 60 and 69 years had a crude rate of 20.49 with a progressive increase in the years 2008 and 2009, reaching 40.02 in 2020. Women in the age group between 70 and 79 years had a crude rate

of 25.48 with a progressive increase, reaching 52.53 in 2020. And women in the age group of 80 years and older had a crude rate of 35.08 with a progressive increase, reaching 97.15 in 2020. Analyzing the mortality rate ratio, it is observed that there was a reduction in the coefficient in the period 2009-2020 compared to the previous period of 1997-2008.

Table 03 shows the mortality rate and the mortality rate ratio for breast cancer in the Northeast region according to age group between 1997 and 2020. It shows the confidence interval (95% CI) in 2008, in the age groups 60-69; 70-79 and 80 or more with the respective values 1.62; 1.61 and 2.04. In 2020 in the same age groups mentioned above, the values correspond to 1.28; 1.32 and 1.41.

The data in Table 04 indicate the result of the analysis of trends in the time series of mortality coefficients carried out by the Joinpoint program considering the crude and adjusted mortality rates per 100,000 inhabitants/year for breast cancer in the Northeast region, in the age groups of 60-69; 70-79 and 80 or more; and in the period between 1997 and 2020. Which were expressed by the APC values (annual percentage variation) that showed in 1997-2000 in women aged 60-69 (APC -1.3), with a considerable increase in 2001-2006 (APC 7.9), evolving with a significant reduction in 2006-2010 (APC 0.4), increasing again in 2010-2016 (APC 4.9) and declining significantly in 2016-2020 (APC 0.2). In women aged 70-79, in the years corresponding to 1997-2003 (APC 2.3), 2003-2006 (APC 8.4), 2006-2013 (APC 3.8), 2013-2018 (APC -3.8) and 2018-2020 (APC -1.5). And finally, in women aged 80 and over in 1997-2001 (APC -2.1), 2001-2007 (APC 11.8), 2007-2011 (APC -1.6), 2011-2014 (APC 10.4) and 2014-2020 (APC 2.3). The average annual percentage change (AAPC) between 1981-2012 shows a significant increase in all age groups, being more prominent in women aged 80 and over.

Table 01: Indicators of information quality by age group in the northeast region between 1997 and 2020.

Sex/Age Range (Years)	Ill-defined causes (%)			Malignant neoplasms, site not specified – C80 (%)		
	1997	2008	2020	1997	2008	2020
< 60	20.9	5.6	5.5	3.3	3.2	1.8
60 - 69	29.3	7.0	5.6	3.9	3.5	2.2
70 - 79	37.7	7.7	5.6	3.3	3.4	2.1
≥ 80	50.2	12.1	8.3	3.9	3.4	1.9
Total	31.4	7.9	6.4	3.5	3.3	2.0

Source: Mortality information system – SIM/Ministry of Health.

Figure 01 – Proportion of ill-defined causes in the northeast region, according to age group between 1996 and 2020.

Source: Mortality information system – SIM/Ministry of Health.

Figure 02 – Proportion of neoplasms without location specification in the northeast region between 1996 and 2020

Source: Mortality information system – SIM/Ministry of Health.

Table 02: Crude rate and mortality rate ratio for breast cancer in the northeast region, according to age group in the periods 1997 - 2008 and 2009 - 2020.

Age range (years)	Mortality rate*				Mortality rate ratio (95% CI)	
	1997	2008	2009	2020	1997-2008	2009-2020
60 – 69	20.49	30.96	32,32	40.02	1.54 (1.28; 1.79) #	1.28 (1.14; 1.44) #
70 – 79	25.48	39.07	41.13	52,53	1.53 (1.26; 1.87) #	1.32 (1.16; 1.51) #
≥ 80	35.08	69.27	71.60	97.15	1.98 (1.56; 2.51) #	1.41 (1.23; 1.63) #
Total	24.18	39.46	41.23	53.12	1.63 (1.46; 1.83) #	1.33 (1.24; 1.44) #

Source: Mortality information system – SIM/Ministry of Health.

Note: * Mortality rate per 100,000 inhabitants/year

** χ^2 for trends

Significant rate ratio (p<0.05)

Table 03: Crude rate and mortality rate ratio for breast cancer in the northeast region, according to age group between 1997 - 2020.

Age range (years)	Mortality rate*	Mortality rate ratio (95% CI)
1997		
60 – 69	20.49	-
70 – 79	25.48	-
≥ 80	35.08	-
	P<0.001	-
2008		
60 – 69	30.96	1.62 (1.37; 1.91) #
70 – 79	39.07	1.61 (1.33; 1.96) #
≥ 80	69.27	2.04 (1.62; 2.59) #
	P<0.001	
2009		
60 – 69	32,32	-
70 – 79	41.13	-
≥ 80	71.60	-
	P<0.001	-
2020		
60 – 69	40.02	1.28 (1.14; 1.44) #
70 – 79	52,53	1.32 (1.16; 1.51) #
≥ 80	97.15	1.41 (1.23; 1.63) #
	P<0.001	

Source: Mortality information system – SIM/Ministry of Health.

Note: * Mortality rate per 100,000 inhabitants/year

** χ^2 for trends

Significant rate ratio (p<0.05)

Table 04 - Joinpoint analysis of crude and adjusted mortality rates per 100,000 inhabitants/year for breast cancer in the northeast region according to age group between 1997 and 2020.

Age range (years)	Trend 01		Trend 02		Trend 03		Trend 04		Trend 05		AAPC [#] 1981-2012
	Period	APC [§]	Period	APC [§]	Period	APC [§]	Period	APC [§]	Period	APC [§]	
60 - 69	1997-2000	-1.3	2000-2006	7.9	2006-2010	0.4	2010-2016	4.1	2016-2020	0.2	3.0(1.9; 4.1)
70 - 79	1997-2003	2.3	2003-2006	8.4	2006 - 2013	2.3	2013 - 2018	-3.8	2018 - 2020	-1.5	3.1(1.9; 4.3)
≥80	1997-2001	-2.1	2001-2007	11.8	2007-2011	-1.6	2011-2014	10.4	2014-2020	2.3	4.3(1.4; 7.2)
Total	1997-2001	0.4	2001-2006	8.6	2006-2010	1.0	2010-2018	3.7	2018-2020	-2.1	3.2(2.1; 4.3)

Source: Mortality information system – SIM/Ministry of Health.

Notice: § Average Annual Percent Change Change)

& Annual Percent Change Change)

F APC is significantly different from 0 (p<0.05)

AAPC is significantly different from 0 (p<0.05)

In most parts of the world, breast cancer is the most common malignant neoplasm among women. This is no different in Brazil.

Variations in breast cancer mortality rates can be attributed to early diagnosis through mammography screening and access to more effective treatments, including adjuvant chemotherapy or tamoxifen, as well as radiotherapy and supportive surgery, in addition to the increase in the frequency of new cases, a fact that occurs due to the variation in risks for the disease.

By studying the temporal trends in breast cancer deaths in northeastern Brazil, a strong upward trend was identified for the period analyzed (1996-2020). Furthermore, according to Barbosa et al., the northeastern region will continue to experience rising mortality rates in the future. Based on mortality projections through 2030, a considerable increase in the breast cancer mortality burden will be observed for all states in northeastern Brazil.

In recent decades, Brazil has experienced demographic and epidemiological changes, which have consequently impacted the profile of diseases and conditions, with increased life expectancy. In this context of epidemiological and demographic transition, a high prevalence of cardiovascular and chronic degenerative diseases, including cancer, has been observed in the Brazilian population. Variations in breast cancer mortality rates can be attributed to early diagnosis through mammography screening and

access to more effective treatments, including adjuvant chemotherapy or tamoxifen, as well as radiotherapy and supportive surgery. This is in addition to the increase in the frequency of new cases, which is due to varying disease risks. One of the most important aspects to be evaluated in Brazil is the distribution of health services across the country's regions. The precariousness of services is related to screening, diagnosis, the stage of the disease at diagnosis, available treatment methods, and, consequently, the impact on survival. The increased mortality from this type of cancer in poorer regions is likely due to delayed diagnosis and the implementation of appropriate treatment, resulting in mortality rates similar to or higher than those in developed countries. The concentration of health services in large urban centers and the lack of organization in the service network mean that, in many municipalities, women are forced to travel to areas with available services, placing a strain on public hospitals in other cities.

CONCLUSION

The upward trend in breast cancer mortality among older women in the Northeast region of Brazil, highlighted in this study, reflects not only the impact of population aging but also the persistent inequality in access to health services. The data analyzed indicate that, despite advances in information systems and the quality of death records, effective breast cancer control remains a challenge, especially among older age groups, where the mortality rate is markedly higher.

The highest mortality rates were recorded in women aged 80 and over, demonstrating the vulnerability of this population to barriers to access to screening, early diagnosis, and timely treatment. The lack of integration between primary and specialized care services, the scarcity of diagnostic resources in small municipalities, and the need to travel to urban centers contribute to the worsening prognosis for these women. Furthermore, it is important to highlight that secondary prevention measures,

such as mammography screening , do not always include older women and are often disregarded in public health strategies, despite the increase in life expectancy. Furthermore, the clinical management of these patients requires an individualized approach, considering their functional conditions, comorbidities, and personal preferences. This requires adequate training and awareness among healthcare professionals.

Therefore, it is urgent to strengthen public policies that ensure equitable access to healthcare services, including expanding mammography coverage , investing in training family health teams, strengthening referral and counter-referral networks , and adopting care protocols that consider the specificities of aging. Analysis of temporal trends in breast cancer mortality among elderly women should inform strategic decisions for organizing care pathways that aim not only to reduce mortality but also to promote the dignity, autonomy, and quality of life of older Brazilian women .

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